

UNIVERSITY OF KHARTOUM
FACULTY OF SCIENCE
TOXIC ORGANISMS RESEARCH CENTRE

TORC

**SCHOLARLY
CONTRIBUTIONS
2021-2024**

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Introduction:

The Toxic Organisms Research Centre (TORC) was established on April 15, 2021, and is affiliated with the Faculty of Science at the University of Khartoum. Since its inception, TORC has played a pivotal role in transforming policies and public awareness regarding venomous species in Sudan. The center has organized two specialized workshops, providing a hub for collaboration among stakeholders from various sectors. It has also been instrumental in raising public awareness about both venomous and non-venomous organisms in Sudan.

TORC Founders:

The original research group that laid the foundation for TORC in 2018 comprised 14 founding members, listed alphabetically with their current administrative roles:

1. Dr. Amna Osman, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
2. Dr. Haseeba Saad, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
3. Dr. Huda Khalid, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
4. Dr. Khairalla M. Saeed Khairalla, Deputy Dean, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Khartoum
5. Dr. Makarim Shabo, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
6. Dr. Manal Siyam, Sudan Natural History Museum, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
7. Dr. Nada Kamal, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
8. Dr. Rania Mohamed Hassan Baleela, Founding Director, TORC, Department of Zoology
9. Dr. Sara Saeed, Director, Sudan Natural History Museum, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
10. Mr. Mohamed Salah, Sudan University of Science and Technology
11. Ms. Entisar Salih, Sudan Natural History Museum, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum
12. Ms. Rayan Hamada, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum

13. Professor Emad Konozi, Director, Africa City of Technology

14. Professor Omran Fadl, Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum

Other experts involved in TORC projects include:

1. Neurologist: Professor Osheik Seidi, Dean, Scientific Research Deanship, UofK
2. Clinical Toxinologist: Dr. Muhammad Elamin Mohamed Osman, National Poisons Information Service (Birmingham unit), Birmingham, UK
3. Physician: Dr. Musadag Dabura, Atbara Hospital, physician specialized in scorpion stings envenomation management
4. Pharmacists: Khartoum Medicines Information Centre staff members, Khartoum State Ministry of Health, Sudan
5. Biodiversity experts: Eng. Abubakr Mohamed, Conflict and Environment Observatory, West Yorkshire, UK and Mr. Mohamed Salah

We work with several stakeholders as well, including:

1. The Federal Ministry of Health
2. National Medical Supplies Fund
3. National Medicines and Poisons Board
4. Civil Defense forces
5. Wildlife Protection Forces
6. Local societies and NGOs
7. National Broadcasting outlets (e.g. Omdurman TV, Omdurman Radio, BN TV, Hawa ALSudan Radio, Newspapers, etc)

The following is a summary of what TORC have published since its establishment in April 2021 up to date. In addition to TORC publications, a list of all other publications on venomous organisms- since colonial time- is also compiled.

TORC Book:

1. Scorpion stings and Snakebites in Sudan: species, geographical distribution, risks and early warning

Authors: Baleela, Rania, . Makarem O. E. Shabo, Saeed, Sara, Khalid, Huda, Siyam, Manal, Salah, Mohamed, Salih, Intisar, Khairalla, Khairalla MohamedSaeed

Description

Presentations were delivered at the inaugural workshop organized by the Toxic Organisms Research Centre, Faculty of Science, University of Khartoum, on May 30, 2022, at the Sudan Natural History Museum in Khartoum. The workshop served as a central platform for discussions among all stakeholders in Sudan, marking a significant milestone in fostering collaborative efforts.

Book link: <https://bit.ly/4fRONyn>

2. Local Production of Scorpion and Snakes Antivenoms Workshop Booklet, 21-22 November 2022

Authors: Baleela, Rania, Saeed, Sara, Khalid, Huda, Siyam, Manal, Ibrahim, Muntasir, Khairalla, Khairalla MohamedSaeed, Musa, Ahmed Mudawi, Abdalla, Eisa Osman El-Amin, Abdelrahim, Hisham Elhag A, Musa, Hassan Hussein, Seidi, Osheik

Book link: <https://bit.ly/3M7ltVk>

Following the workshop, TORC members Dr. Huda Khalid, Dr. Makarem Shabo, and Dr. Khairalla MohamedSaeed initiated primary experiments in March 2023, with funding provided by the Scientific Research Deanship at the University of Khartoum. The venom was lyophilized at Professor Emad Konozy's laboratory in the Africa City of Technology, and the research was carried out at the Department of Pharmacology & Toxicology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine,

UofK. Unfortunately, due to the outbreak of war in April 2023, the collected venom samples and live animals were lost.

TORC Papers:

1. **Baleela**, R.M.H., Mohammad, A. & Saeed, S.A.K. The role of social media in public health awareness during times of war in Sudan: snakebites and scorpion stings. *BMC Public Health* 24, 1752 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-19156-8>
2. **Baleela**, RMH, Elamin, MEMO, Mohammad, A, Saeed, SAK. Medically important snakes in Sudan: an overview of distribution, clinical features, and present challenges (Accepted and will be available online soon).
<https://apps.crossref.org/pendingpub/pendingpub.html?doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrae063>
3. **Khalid**, H., Siyam, Elamin, M., & Azrag, R. (2023). Scorpion stings envenomation in Sudan: a retrospective study of hospital-based incidence. *Toxicology Communications*, 7(1), 2285123. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/24734306.2023.2285123>

TORC Identification cards:

I have been working on this project for several years, gathering data from various sources (i.e. books, specialized websites and papers) and consulting with field experts (i.e. Dr. Manal Siyam, Ust. Entisar Salih, Mr. Mohamed Salah and Eng. Abubakr Mohamed). The project is now complete, providing accessible information in simple Arabic for community members, along with detailed guidance for medical personnel. You can access the ID cards for Sudanese species in PDF format here:

<https://bit.ly/3YMeBnE>. Another version is available in photographic format.

The project has also expanded to include ID cards for species from the MENA region and East Africa, created in response to numerous inquiries, particularly from Saudi Arabia, followed by Yemen and Oman.

TORC Sudan Fauna and Flora Project:

This is a project that aims to enrich the Sudanese presence online via providing Research Grade photos of organisms to the scientific community at large. It includes both plant and animal species, focusing on their distribution, behavior, ecology, and conservation status. The project utilizes a multidisciplinary approach, combining field surveys, molecular techniques, and ecological modeling to generate detailed data on Sudan's biodiversity. By understanding the rich fauna and flora of Sudan, the project seeks to contribute to conservation efforts, sustainable management of natural resources, and the promotion of biodiversity awareness and education.

Please Note:

This project is open for contributors. If you have a photo that you wish to share, create your iNaturalist account (<https://www.inaturalist.org/>) and choose Sudan Fauna and Flora as the project where you wish to contribute. You will be the owner, the platform will help you classify it, species experts will confirm your classification and Sudan presence will get richer!

The project can be accessed through iNaturalist here:

<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/sudan-fauna-and-flora>

TORC Field reports

Field reports are prepared for every location we surveyed and distributed to the local authorities and societies we worked with. Available upon request.

TORC Facebook group: Scorpions and Snakes of Sudan

This is the social media window presence of the Toxic Organisms Research Centre where we serve the community directly. The community reached 9200 members in 20 months. It was established on January 15th 2023.

Link to Facebook group: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/574721000781492>

Specialized Telegram group Targeting physicians and the medical professionals

Established to provide medical practitioners in Sudan with updated and accurate management protocols for scorpion stings and snakebites envenomation.

Link to the Telegram group: <https://t.me/+RzzCKV1AX1k3ZWRk>

Rania Baleela Presentations:

1. **Climate change, social injustice and venomous organisms: an update about the situation in Sudan**

Authors: Rania Baleela, Manal Siyam, Intesar Salih, Mohamed Salah, Sara Saeed, Makarem Shabo.

Flash talk Speaker: Dr. Rania Baleela, at the International Society on Toxinology, 2021. Won the Best Research Prize.

Poster can be accessed in the link: <https://bit.ly/3Xa3Wly>

2. Scorpion Stings in Sudan: Venom, War & Gold Rush

Invited speaker: Dr. Rania Baleela, at the Knowledge Transfer Club, Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine, United Kingdom

This presentation was prepared for Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine's Knowledge Transfer Club and delivered on July 4th, 2024. It outlines the complex interplay of environmental, social, and political factors influencing scorpion envenomation in Sudan, emphasizing the need for comprehensive public health strategies and ongoing research to reduce the impact of scorpion stings on affected populations.

Link to the presentation PowerPoint slides: <https://bit.ly/4eJ3u4u>

3. Local antivenom production project

Invited speaker: Dr. Rania Baleela, presented at the MENATOX2023.

This is a presentation about the status of antivenom in Sudan at that time and our efforts at TORC to locally produce antivenoms.

Link to presentation: <https://bit.ly/3WTSqJA>

4. Harnessing the Power of social media in the time of war!

Authors: Rania Baleela & Sara Saeed

Presenter: Dr. Rania Baleela, presented at the MENATOX2024

In this presentation we introduced the audience to the usefulness of social media in raising awareness of communities as well as a pilot data collection source for planning next field ones.

Link to presentation: <https://bit.ly/3XapD5d>

List of all other publications on snakes and scorpions from Sudan:

1. Ahmed, M. A., Massaad, S. O., Abdalla, K.O. et al. "Snake Bites Envenoming Among Children in Gadarif, Eastern Sudan" *J Clin Toxicol*, p. 9:6, 2019.
2. Balfour, A. "Fourth report of the Wellcome Tropical Research Laboratories at the Gordon Memorial College, VOLUME B. General Science" BAILLIERE, TINDALL & COX, 8, Henrietta Street, Covent Garden, LONDON, Khartoum, 1911.
3. Balfour, A. "Third Report of the Wellcome Research Laboratories at the Gordon Memorial College" BAILLIERE, TINDALL & COX, 8, Henrietta Street, Covent Gaudkn, London, Khartoum, 1908.
4. Barbour, T. "Reptiles and amphibians from Eastern Sudan" *Proceedings of the Biological Society of Washington*, Washington, 1913.
5. Broadley, D. G. "A collection of snakes from eastern Sudan, with the description of a new species of *Telescopus* Wagler, 1830 (Reptilia: Ophidia)" *Journal of African Zoology*, vol. 108, no. 2, pp. 201-208, 1994.
6. Corkill, N. and Kirk, R. "Poisoning by the Sudan mole viper *Atractaspis microlepidota* Günther" *Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 376–384, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0035-9203\(54\)90136-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0035-9203(54)90136-4), 1954.
7. Corkill, N. L. "Notes on Sudan snakes" *Sudan Government Museum (Natural History)*, pp. 4-40, August 1935.
8. Corkill, N. L. "Snake stories from Kordofan" *Sudan Notes and Records*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 243-253, 1935.
9. Khalid, H. and Azrag, R. S. "Retrospective hospital-based study on snakebite envenomation in Sudan" *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*, p. 115: 992–997, 2021.
10. King, H. H. (1925). Notes on Sudan scorpions. *Sudan Notes and Records*.
11. Kirk, R. "Poisonous snakes of the Sudan" *Sudan Wild life and sport*, vol. 2, p. 17–27, 1951.

12. Loveridge, A. "On Snakes Collected in The Anglo-Egyptian Sudan By J. S. Owen, Esq." *Sudan Notes and Records*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 37-56, 1955.
13. Loveridge, A. "Revision of the African snakes of the genera *Dromophis* and *Psammophis*" *Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology*, at Harvard College, CAMBRIDGE, MASS., U. S. A, 1940.
14. Mohamed, A. A. E.-R., Mohamed, A. A. S., Mahmoud, Z. N. "Snakes of Jebel Al Dair Biosphere Reserve, North Kordofan State" *Ecol Conserv Sci.*, vol. 2, no. 4, 2023.
15. Mohammed A. A., Ahmed, Ismail E., Mahmoud, Z. N. *Snakes of Sudan: New Locality Records and an Update*. In: *Innovations in Biological Science Vol. 4*. B P International, pp. 88-104. ISBN 978-81-973053-0-6, 2024.
16. Osman, HEI and Elsir, NT. The snakes of Khartoum province. *The Snake*, vol. 20 PP 74-79, 1988.
17. Saeed, S., Osman, O. and Allam, T. "Some Preliminary Studies on the Haemolytic Activity of the Venom of Four Viper Species" *ACT-Biotechnology Research Communications*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 56-59, 2011.
18. Siyam, M.; Dunlop, JA, Kovařík, F, Mohammad, A. Additions to the distribution of Sudanese scorpions. *Zoosyst. Evol.* 99 (1) 2023, 45–53 | DOI 10.3897/zse.99.90875.
19. Spawls, S. and Branch, B. *The Dangerous Snakes of Africa*, First ed., London: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc, 2020.
20. Spawls, S., Mazuch, T. and Mohammad, A. *Handbook of Amphibians and Reptiles of North- East Africa*, London: Bloomsbury Wildlife, 2023.
21. Wuster, W. and Broadley, D. "A new species of spitting cobra (*Naja*) from north-eastern Africa (Serpentes: Elapidae)" *J. Zool., Lond.*, vol. 259, no. DOI:10.1017/S0952836902003333, p. 345–359, 2003.

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